

Appendix: Apopemptic Prayers in Greco-Roman Poetry

Here are listed all of the poetic ἀποπομπαί in ancient Greek and Roman literature¹ that I have been able to find,² for the benefit of any reader who would like to check the significance of the parallels between the Apollonian and Catullan passages against other examples of this type of prayer. While I can hardly claim that this list is comprehensive, it is to my knowledge the most thorough compilation of its kind. The list, given in roughly chronological order, includes the *avertendum*, or the evil that the speaker would like to avert; I have also indicated instances in which this evil is (or could be associated with) madness.³

Author	Citation	<i>Avertendum</i>	Madness?
Homer	<i>Od.</i> 15.358–360	Death from grief	
Theognis	351–354	Poverty	
Simonides	<i>AP</i> 7.496	Landscape treacherous to sailors ⁴	
Aeschylus	<i>Ag.</i> 1567–1576	The family δαίμων	μανία

¹ I have left out of account apopemptic prayers in Jewish and Christian poetry (which at any rate mostly postdate Catullus), though these texts afford some excellent examples of the form (e.g., Gregory of Nazianzus *carmen* 55 [coll. 1399–1401 Migne]). I have also excluded the few non-literary verse examples my research has turned up, such as *Inscriptiones creticae* 2.223–225, no. XIX.7 Guarducci (a Hellenistic-era apotropaic spell inscribed on a lead tablet from Phalasarina) and *I.Pergamon* 324.38–39 Fränkel = *Epigr. Gr.* 1035.28–29 Kaibel (a second-century CE inscription recording an oracle from Clarian Apollo concerning the mitigation of plague).

² This list has been assembled for the most part by collecting citations from the following sources:

Conington/Nettleship 1871, ad Verg. *Aen.* 8.484; Jebb 1888, ad Soph. *Ant.* 372; Schmidt 1891; Morawski 1903, 14–21; Wunsch 1911; Weinreich 1929, 169–194; 1939; 1942, 41–70; 1975, 353–357; 1979; Keyßner 1932, 114–117; Norden 1939, 125; Fraenkel 1950, ad Aesch. *Ag.* 1573; Gow 1952, ad Theoc. *Id.* 6.24; Zuntz 1955, 122 with n. 5; Bömer 1958, ad Ov. *Fast.* 3.494; Breitenstein 1966, 69; Nisbet/Hubbard 1970, ad Hor. *Odes* 1.21.13; Versnel 1976, 389–394; 1977, 41–42; Williams 1978, 97; Kroll 1980, ad Catull. 63.91, 92; Hopkinson 1984, ad Call. *Hymn* 6.116–117; Fedeli 1985, ad Prop. 3.8.20; Hollis 1990, ad Call. *Hecale* fr. 47.10–11; Newman 1990, 216; Fantham 1998, ad Ov. *Fast.* 4.116; McKeown 1998, ad Ov. *Am.* 2.10.15–16; Morisi 1999, ad Catull. 63.91, 92; Gale 2000, 76 n. 63; Ricciardelli 2000, ad *Hymn. Orph.* 3.14, 14.14, 66.12; Maltby 2002, ad Tib. 1.33–34; Gibson 2003, ad Ov. *Ars am.* 3.247–248; Horsfall 2008, ad Verg. *Aen.* 2.190.

³ My inclusion and exclusion of some passages could be quibbled over, as it can sometimes be difficult to draw a sharp line between an ἀποπομπή and various other types of negative prayers, wishes, exhortations, *vel sim.* Thus, for instance, I have left out passages like Aesch. *PV* 972–973 and Lucill. *AP* 11.196.5–6, as in these cases we do find speakers wishing present evils upon their enemies, but without a marked sense of *sending away* said evils (cf. Friis Johansen/Whittle 1980, ad Aesch. *Suppl.* 376). On similar grounds I have excluded Timocreon fr. 731 *PMG*, which, as an unattainable wish, does not seem to represent a genuine effort to avert the evil in question (blind Wealth); cf. Schmidt 1891, 563. Likewise, in *AP* 5.10 (by Alcaeus of Messene), a sentiment that could have been cast as an apopemptic prayer is rather expressed in a series of rhetorical questions. I have also excluded passages like Hor. *Odes* 1.26.1–3, which appear to me to refer to a metaphorical ‘dismissal’ of certain mental states or concerns (see Nisbet/Hubbard 1970, ad 1.26.2) rather than to a concrete expulsion of evil (cf. Weinreich 1942, 49–54). But despite such debatable judgment calls, this list should be extensive enough to serve the heuristic purpose of showcasing some general trends in the exploitation of the apopemptic form in Greco-Roman poetry.

⁴ For the rationale of the wish expressed in this poem, see Sider 2020, ad Simon. *Epigr.* 39.4.

	<i>Prom.</i> 864	Love such as the Aegyptids enjoyed	
	<i>Sept.</i> 255, 626–630	Zeus’ wrath (x2)	
	<i>Suppl.</i> 376	Ritual pollution	
	<i>Suppl.</i> 524–530	The hubris of the Aegyptids	ἄτα
	<i>Suppl.</i> 679–685	Civil strife and sickness	
Sophocles	<i>Ant.</i> 370–375	Friendship with the disreputable	
	<i>El.</i> 644–647	Ill-omened dreams	
	<i>OT</i> 190–196 ⁵	Plague	
Euripides	<i>Hec.</i> 72, 96–97	An ill-omened dream	
	<i>Hec.</i> 1276	A foreboding oracle	
	<i>Hel.</i> 360	Troubles (κακά)	
	<i>Heracl.</i> 770–776	An invading army	
	<i>HF</i> 649–654	Old age	
	<i>Med.</i> 632–635	Immoderate love	
	fr. 453.9–12 Nauck	Civil discord	μαιομένα Ἔρις
	fr. 848 Nauck	Association w/ one who dishonors his parents	
	fr. 1060 Nauck	An invading army	
Callimachus	<i>Hec.</i> 47.10–11	Sailing under a bad omen?	
	<i>Hymn</i> 2.113	Blame	
	<i>Hymn</i> 6.116–117	Friendship with an enemy of Demeter	
Theocritus	<i>Id.</i> 6.24	A foreboding oracle	
Apollonius	<i>Argon.</i> 4.445–449	Eros	ἄτη
Leonidas of Tarentum	<i>AP</i> 6.302	Mice	
‘Ariston’	<i>AP</i> 6.303	Mice	
Nicander	<i>Ther.</i> 186, 305	Snakebite (x2)	

⁵ This choral ode may be meant to imitate the apotropaic variety of paean; see Rutherford 2001, 36–38, 109.

Leonidas of Alexandria	<i>AP</i> 9.356	Blame	
Pacuvius	fr. 75 Schierl ⁶	Madness	<i>amentia</i>
Terence	<i>Andr.</i> 232–233	An incompetent midwife	
	<i>Phorm.</i> 976–979	A damnable man	
[Moschus]	<i>Megara</i> 123–125	An ill-omened dream	
Meleager	<i>AP</i> 5.178, 179.9–10	Eros (x2)	
Archias	<i>AP</i> 5.98	Aphrodite's arrows	
Anon.	<i>Carm. pop.</i> 13 Page (<i>PMG</i> 859 = Festus [p. 414 Lindsay]) ⁷	The ill-omened <i>strix</i>	
Catullus	14.21–23	Terrible poets	
	33.5–6	Clothes-thieves at the baths	
	44.18–21	A cold and cough	
	63.91–93	Madness	<i>furor</i>
Tibullus	1.1.33–34	Flock predation	
	1.6.85–86	Punishments for infidelity	
	2.1.18–20	Rural evils	
	2.5.79–80	Prodigies	
[Tibullus]	3.4.1–4	A bad dream	
	3.10.1–8	Disease and other evils	
Propertius	2.4.17–18	Love of girls	
	2.12.18–20	Cupid	
	3.8.20	<i>A lenta puella</i>	
	4.6.9	Deceit	

⁶ Ancient grammarians regularly glossed *averruncare*, the archaic religious term used in this prayer, with *avertere*, ‘turn away’ (see Schierl 2006, 225–226 and *TLL s.v.*; see further the clearly apopemptic adaptations of this line in Arnobius [*Adv. nat.* 1.32] and Ambrose [*De fide* 1.9.60, 1.11.73], cited by Otto 1890, 18), so this brief prayer likely does have (or was perceived to have) a specifically apopemptic force. *N.b.* also the (no doubt parodic) near-quotation of this line in Lucil. fr. 653 Marx.

⁷ The date of this poem is difficult to determine (Wilamowitz 1925, 304), but as it was collected already in the Augustan era by the grammarian Verrius Flaccus (whose *De verborum significatione*, as epitomized by Festus, preserves this specimen), I consider it more than likely to predate Catullus in the Late Republican period.

Vergil	<i>G.</i> 3.513	Plague	<i>error</i>
	<i>Aen.</i> 2.190–191	Destruction	
	<i>Aen.</i> 3.265–266	An unfavorable prophecy	
	<i>Aen.</i> 3.620	The Cyclops	
	<i>Aen.</i> 8.484	Savage deeds	
Horace	<i>Epodes</i> 5.49–54	Magic	
	<i>Odes</i> 1.21.13–16	War, famine, and plague	
	<i>Odes</i> 1.28.25–29	Rough weather	
	<i>Odes</i> 1.35.33–40	(Civil) war	
	<i>Odes</i> 3.27.21–24	Storms	
	<i>Odes</i> 4.1.1–28	Venus	
Ovid ⁸	<i>Her.</i> 16.219–220	Eating w/ one's lover and her husband	
	<i>Her.</i> 20.121–122	Anxiety as caused by an ill lover	
	<i>Am.</i> 1.14.41	Sickness	
	<i>Am.</i> 2.9.15–16	Love	
	<i>Am.</i> 2.10.16–18	Life without love	
	<i>Am.</i> 3.11a.16	Shame of being seen by a successful rival	
	<i>Ars am.</i> 3.247–248	A bad hair day	
	<i>Fast.</i> 3.494	A dark complexion	
	<i>Fast.</i> 4.116	Mad impiety	<i>furor</i>
	<i>Fast.</i> 4.747–767	Assorted agrarian woes	
	<i>Fast.</i> 4.923–932	Rust	
	<i>Pont.</i> 1.10.19–20	Tomis' 'delights'	
	<i>Pont.</i> 4.6.35–36	Brutus' rhetoric	
[Ovid]	<i>Epiced. Drusi</i> 450	Fearful old age	
Anon.	<i>Priapea</i> 86.19–21	Theft	

⁸ Ovid's unparalleled predilection for this figure is noted by Morawski 1903, 16.

Lucillius	<i>AP</i> 11.394	Madness (making guests go hungry after inviting them to hear one's poetry) ⁹	μανία
[Seneca]	<i>Oct.</i> 756–759	An ill-omened dream	
Stattius	<i>Silv.</i> 4.8.16–17	Envy	
Martial	10.72.4–7	Debasing flattery of the emperor	
Philippus of Thessalonica	<i>AP</i> 6.240	Sickness	
Dionysius Periegetes	741–742	The Massagetae	
[Dionysius]	<i>De avibus</i> 2.8	The halcyon	
Serenus Sammonicus	947–948	Fractures and dislocations	
[Orpheus]	<i>Hymn</i> 3.14	Fears	
	<i>Hymn</i> 11.23	Panic	πανικός οἴστρος
	<i>Hymn</i> 12.14–16	Disease, ruin, and death	
	<i>Hymn</i> 14.14	Pollution and death	
	<i>Hymn</i> 19.18–19	Zeus' anger as expressed by his thunderbolt	
	<i>Hymn</i> 23.7–8	Earthquakes	
	<i>Hymn</i> 36.16	Disease and pains	
	<i>Hymn</i> 37.7–8	Divine wrath	
	<i>Hymn</i> 39.9–10	Divine wrath in the form of mental disturbances caused by apparitions ¹⁰	φαντασῖαι, ψυχῆς ἐκπλήκτου ἀνάγκαι
	<i>Hymn</i> 58.10	Base impulses	

⁹ For the social faux pas here dramatically figured as 'madness' by the parasite-like speaker, see Larossa 2010, 96–98. I find this reading more convincing than the supposition that the 'madness' in question consists of composing (inferior) poetry (Floridi 2014, ad loc. [= 127.4 in her edition]).

¹⁰ On the nature of these disturbances, see the discussion in Hunsucker 1974, 189–191; in general on the *Orphic Hymns'* preoccupation with madness, which is a relatively frequent *avertendum* in their apopemptic prayers, see Graf 2009.

	<i>Hymn</i> 71.10–12	Madness	ψυχῆς οἶστρος (cf. μαίνει, 6)
	<i>Hymn</i> 73.7–9	Life-destroying troubles	
	<i>Hymn</i> 77.10	Forgetfulness	
Ausonius	<i>Epist.</i> 27.58–66	Nemesis	
Proclus	<i>Hymn</i> 6.5–6, 7.43–46	Diseases (x2)	
Macedonius of Thessalonica	<i>AP</i> 5.224	Eros' arrows ¹¹	

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¹¹ Doubtless many more poems now lost to us contained further literary depictions of ἀποπομπαί; one likely candidate, to judge by its title, is Sophron's mime *Women Who Say They Expel the Goddess* (Γυναῖκες αἱ τὰν θεὸν φαντι ἐξελάω, fr. 3 Rusten/Cunningham).

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